

Epoxy Acids of *Mucuna prurita* Seed Oil**

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Oil from the seed of *Mucuna prurita* (Leguminosae, Hindi, —Jangli Kawanch) contains previously unidentified *cis*-12, 13-epoxyoctadec-*trans*-9-enoic (1%) and the more common vernolic [*cis*-12, 13-epoxyoctadec-*cis*-9-enoic] (4%) acid. Gunstone's procedure of direct acetolysis of oil containing epoxy acids in minor amounts was adopted to characterize the epoxy acids in the oil. The techniques used in isolation and identification of the acids included thin-layer and column chromatography, IR, UV, NMR and chemical reactions (*viz.*, reduction and oxidative cleavage) coupled with GLC.

M. prurita is a wild variety of species *M. pruriens*, which is cultivated for its brown valvate legumes and used as a vegetable. An early report¹ from this laboratory about 1.3% of epoxy acid in *M. pruriens* led to the present compositional study of an allied species. Fatty acid composition of the oil has been determined by chromatographic techniques.

Experimental

The presence of epoxy function was revealed by on-the-plate test with picric acid². For determination of epoxyacyl content of oil, hydrogen bromide titration was performed at 3° by the procedure of Harris *et al.*³. Analytical TLC was carried out on 0.25 mm layers of Silica Gel G developed in Et₂O-hexane-acetic acid (20 : 80 : 1, v/v/v). Dihydroxy acid methyl esters were analyzed by TLC on H₃BO₃-Si Gel G⁴ and AgNO₃-Si Gel G⁵ also. The spots were visualized by spraying with H₂SO₄-K₂Cr₂O₇ followed by charring. Mixed dihydroxy esters were fractionated by column chromatography using silver nitrate-impregnated silica using a mixture of ether in hexane in increasing proportions. GLC analyses of methyl esters were carried out as described by Miwa⁶. A Perkin-Elmer Model 154, equipped with thermal conductivity detector, using stainless steel packed column (2 m × 3 mm) coated with diethylene glycol succinate (DEGS, 15% on chromosorb W, 45-60 mesh) was employed. The separations were carried out at 100 and 200 chart speed 0.76 m/hr with a hydrogen flow of 70 ml/min. The dihydroxy esters were cleaved before and after hydrogenation by the permanganate-periodate method of von Rudloff⁷ and the products were subsequently chromatographed on GLC columns after esterification. IR spectra were determined with Perkin-Elmer Model 621 spectrometer. NMR spectra were run in CCl₄ at 60 MHz with TMS as internal standard, chemical shifts are expressed in τ . A Beckman DK-2A instrument was used to determine UV spectra.

Oil was extracted from the ground seeds with petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) and the methyl esters prepared by NaOMe transesterification⁸. A portion of the oil was acetylated⁹, saponified and acidified, the resulting acids were separated into oxygenated and non-oxygenated fractions by partitioning between 80% methanol and petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°)⁹. The crude dihydroxy acids and non-oxygenated acids obtained from methanol and petroleum ether extracts respectively were esterified with 2% HCl in MeOH by refluxing for 2 hr. Composition of non-oxygenated methyl esters was determined by TLC-GLC.

The analytical values of seeds and oil, determined according to the procedures recommended by the AOCS method¹¹, are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA ON *M. prurita* SEEDS AND OIL

Oil%	4.2
Moisture%	5.6
Protein content N × 6.25%	30.0
Refractive index, n_D^{40}	1.4840
Iodine value (Wijs)	98.0
Saponification value	194.0
Oxirane oxygen, %	0.25
HBr equiv. (% epoxyoleic)	4.87
Unsaponifiable content%	2.8
Ultraviolet (UV)	Usn ¹¹
Infrared (IR)	840 cm ⁻¹

The non-oxygenated esters when analyzed by GLC, had the composition shown in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The *M. prurita* seeds contained 4.2% oil (dry basis). The UV spectrum showed no conjugation in the oil and its methyl ester. The IR spectrum of

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TABLE 2—FATTY ACID COMPOSITION OF *M. prurita* OIL.

Component	%
16 : 0	21.0
18 : 0	2.7
18 : 1	16.8
18 : 2	46.1
18 : 3	8.4
Vernolic	4.0*
<i>cis</i> -12,13-epoxyoctadec- <i>trans</i> -9-enoic	1.0*

* Calculated with the help of HBr titration, partitioning, and column separation.

the oil showed a very weak band at 840 cm^{-1} , attributed to the epoxy group¹⁰. Picric acid TLC² also revealed the presence of epoxy function. The epoxy content in the oil was found to be 5% (based on HBr-titration and partitioning). The possibility for the occurrence of oxygenated acids other than

epoxy in the oil was ruled out on the basis of IR and TLC.

Characterization of epoxy acids :

The epoxy acids of the oil were characterized as their corresponding dihydroxy acids formed by the direct acetolysis of oil followed by saponification⁹. The mixed dihydroxy esters on ordinary TLC migrated as a single spot whereas on Ag^+ /TLC gave two spots differing in their R_f values. Separation of these mixed dihydroxy esters by argentation column chromatography gave two fractions (major Fraction 1, 80% : minor Fraction 2, 20% by wt. of the total hydroxy esters).

Characterization of Fraction 1 :

The structure of the major dihydroxy ester (Fraction 1) was established by elemental analysis,

Scheme 1

catalytical hydrogenation, oxidative cleavage, and comparison of its TLC, IR and NMR characteristics with that of an authentic sample of methyl *threo*-12,13-dihydroxyoctadec-*cis*-9-enoate prepared from *V. anthelmintica* seed oil by the same treatment. Anal. Calcd for $C_{19}H_{36}O_4$: C, 69.51; H, 10.97. Found: C, 69.84; H, 10.91. It absorbed one mole of hydrogen (one double bond). A co-TLC on ordinary, silver nitrate and boric acid-impregnated plates with an authentic sample showed the identity of the two dihydroxy esters. The IR and NMR spectra were superimposable with that of authentic sample. Permanganate-periodate cleavage⁷ of this fraction as such and after hydrogenation also confirmed the proposed structure (Scheme 1). Therefore, the structure of Fraction 1 is established as methyl *threo*-12,13-dihydroxyoctadec-*cis*-9-enoate (IIa).

Characterization of Fraction 2 :

Anal. Calcd for $C_{19}H_{36}O_4$: C, 69.51; H, 10.97. Found: C, 69.45; H 11.0. Absorbed one mole of hydrogen (one double bond). On Ag⁺/TLC Fraction 2 (minor) migrated ahead of Fraction 1 (major). Comparison of this fraction with that of the standard diol (from *V. anthelmintica*) by TLC on boric acid-impregnated Silica Gel G demonstrated that this had also *threo* configuration. The IR spectrum showed the bands at 3450 (due to

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-OH), 1740 (due to ester-C=O-group) and 970 (due to *trans* double bond) cm^{-1} . The ¹H NMR gave signals at τ 4.54 (2H, olefinic protons), 6.34 (s, 3H, ester methyl protons), 6.65 [4H. 2H (-CH-O) + 2H(-OH)], 7.76 (2H, α to the carbonyl function), 8.0 (protons α to the double bond), 8.7 (br, s, shielded methylene protons), 9.12 (rough t, 3H, terminal methyl protons). On D₂O shake the signal at τ 6.67 was reduced and integrated for two protons only (2H, -CH-O) indicating that the hydroxyl protons signal was merged with the signal of -CH-O. When subjected to splitting by permanganate-periodate¹² as such and after hydrogenation, the cleavage products were the same as in the case of Fraction 1 (Scheme 1). This indicated that the position of the hydroxyls and the double bond is the same in both the fractions. The presence of a distinct band near 960 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum proves that the double bond is *trans* in this fraction. The most significant parameter in ¹H NMR for the determination of the configuration of a double bond is the coupling constant between the alkenyl protons. But in this case, as for most isolated double bonds, it is not possible to measure coupling constant¹², but a small chemical shift difference in alkenyl protons of Fraction 2 (τ 4.54) and authentic sample (τ 4.6) giving different and distinct absorption¹² is a conclusive evidence for the presence of *trans* and *cis* double bonds in

Fraction 2 and authentic sample respectively. On the basis of elemental analysis, reduction, oxidative cleavage, direct argentation and boric acid TLC, IR and NMR data Fraction 2 was found to be methyl *threo*-12,13-dihydroxyoctadec-*trans*-9-enoate (IIb).

As no dihydroxy acid was obtained from the whole oil by solvent partition procedure when the acetolysis step is omitted, the dihydroxy acids are not present in the crude oil but must be formed by acetolysis of the epoxy acids. The presence of weak IR band at 970 cm^{-1} in the oxygenated oil concentrate showed that the acid with *trans* unsaturation is not an artifact formed during the chemical treatment of the oil (acetolysis followed by saponification) but is originally present in the oil.

The dihydroxy esters (Fraction 1 & 2) derived from the epoxy acids of *M. prurita* oil were identified as methyl *threo*-12,13-dihydroxyoctadec-*cis*-9-enoate (Ia) and methyl *threo*-12,13-dihydroxyoctadec-*trans*-9-enoate (Ib). These results demonstrate conclusively that the original epoxy acids are *cis*-12, 13-epoxyoctadec-*cis*-9-enoic (Vernolic) and *cis*-12,13-epoxyoctadec-*trans*-9-enoic acids.

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